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Report

Management and multi-disciplinary approach in complex cases of PANS-H63D-Multisystemic Instability Syndrome

Abstract

This case series aims to elucidate the clinical presentation and management strategies employed in patients diagnosed with PANS-H63D-Multisystemic Instability Syndrome. This rare condition is characterized by an interplay between chronic-progressive Pediatric Acute-onset Neuropsychiatric Syndrome (PANS) in adults, and H63D Syndrome, induced by a homozygous H63D mutation in the HFE gene affecting iron metabolism. The report offers an overview of diagnostic workup, therapeutic interventions, and prognostic indicators, while providing insight into the multisystemic instabilities observed in these patients.

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Introduction

This scholarly clinical report serves as a seminal overview of an increasingly recognized, multifaceted syndrome in the specialized arena of clinical neurology. The syndrome is characterized by an intricate confluence of three major factors: a specific course of symptoms and manifestation of Pediatric Acute-onset Neuropsychiatric Syndrome (PANS), an often missed underlying mitochondrial dysfunction, and a specific H63D mutation in the HFE gene, which has a consequential impact on iron metabolism (H63D-Syndrome).³⁻¹¹ Compiled through an aggregate analysis of multiple case reports, this comprehensive review aims to define the landscape of diagnostic protocols, possible therapeutic interventions, and prognostic indicators. The report underscores the pervasive multi-systemic instabilities commonly associated with this complex syndrome. In doing so, it seeks to elucidate the multi-layered challenges and variances inherent in the challenging clinical management and understanding of this pathological entity.

Clinical Presentation

PANS in adults: a Lifelong and potentially progressive clinical course

While PANS typically originates during childhood or adolescence, usually in the setting of an acute infection, its ramifications can extend well into adulthood, often adopting a more complex and systemic profile. This nuanced transition from pediatric to adult PANS is frequently marked by the emergence of multi-organ systemic manifestations that go beyond neuropsychiatric symptoms. Affected organs frequently include but are not limited to the liver, brain, innate immune system, skin, and sympathetic nervous system. The clinical course in adults diverges from its pediatric predecessor by often adopting a slow, wave-like progression. Each episodic flare

is characterized by an acute exacerbation of severe symptoms, akin to the pediatric presentation, but what distinguishes the adult form is a proclivity for residual symptomatology to linger following each episode. This residual symptom burden contributes to a baseline functional decline, giving the disease course a potentially progressive nature over the long term. PANS in adults should definitely not be misconceived as a simple extension of the pediatric form. Instead, it exhibits a unique clinical identity characterized by a chronic, and at times progressive, disease trajectory that involves a more widespread systemic involvement. Therefore, comprehensive longitudinal care involving vigilant monitoring and multi-systemic treatment strategies are essential for an effective management of this syndrome.¹⁵⁻¹⁹

PANS-induced Mitochondrial Dysfunction

Interactions between the dysregulated innate immune system and inherited factors lead to disruptions in kynurenine metabolism. Measurement of enzymatic activity downstream of Kynurenin-3-Monooxygenase (KMO) appears to remain largely unaffected, suggesting the locus of the dysfunction may be at or upstream of KMO. The syndrome is often accompanied by elevated postprandial lactate levels, indicative of a shift away from aerobic metabolism, thus revealing a mitochondrial dysfunction component.¹³⁻²⁵

H63D Syndrome

Latest by early adulthood, a homozygous H63D mutation in the HFE gene becomes clinically relevant. This mutation leads to a rare but well-documented pathology of iron metabolism where non-transferrin-bound iron accumulates due to persistent non-reactive hypotransferrinemia. Iron-chelation therapy and phlebotomies are generally contraindicated, particularly when ferritin levels are within the lower normal range.^{7,8,9}

Treatment Strategy

Our therapeutic approach aims to maximize patient life quality through supportive, protective and regulatory pharmacotherapy. Off-label medications are very carefully selected to minimize polypharmacy, and the regimen is tailored by specialists well-versed in maximizing therapeutic synergies. The primary focus of our therapeutic approach should center on two pivotal aspects: intensive anti-inflammatory measures and stabilization of dysautonomias. It is crucial to note that standard inflammatory markers like C-reactive protein (CRP) and Interleukin-6 (IL-6) etc. often fail to capture the low-grade inflammation associated with this condition. Instead, one should consider evaluating the Kynurenine/Tryptophan (K/T) ratio as a way more sensitive diagnostic parameter.

Anti-Inflammatory Measures

Strong and effective anti-inflammatory interventions are paramount, considering that oxidative stress and inflammation are key players in the pathophysiology of this syndrome. However, conventional markers may not be sensitive enough to capture the nuances of inflammation in these patients.

Kynurenine/Tryptophan (K/T) Ratio

This ratio can serve as a sensitive marker for ongoing inflammatory processes and stress reactions in the body. It allows a specific estimation of the activity of indoleamine 2,3-dioxygenase (IDO), which tends to be upregulated in inflammatory conditions. An elevated K/T ratio could therefore serve as an indicator for IDO activity and, by extension, inflammatory processes that may not be captured by standard tests. Monitoring this ratio can be especially relevant when considering the modulation of the inflammatory response, for example, through the use of anti-inflammatory medications or agents that may interfere with Kynurenine/Tryptophan metabolism.¹²⁻¹⁴

Stabilization of Dysautonomias

Attention should also be given to stabilizing dysautonomic symptoms, which are often a clinical hallmark of this condition. This may involve modulation of catecholamines, especially adrenaline and noradrenaline, and firming up the Hypothalamic-Pituitary-Adrenal (HPA) axis. The HPA axis plays a significant role in stress response and autonomic regulation; therefore, therapies aiming at stabilizing it could have far-reaching benefits.

Cautionary Notes

Despite cognitive impairments, the younger patients are not suffering from dementia and appreciate a clear and straightforward communication about their medical situation. The syndrome's complex nature necessitates a highly customized, adaptable treatment approach, as textbook guidelines are often insufficient for such unique, multi-systemic conditions. The patients' cooperation, trust and compliance are therefore crucial.

Conclusion

Based on the existing data, the intricate presentation of this syndrome - essentially a meta-syndrome encompassing PANS, mitochondrial dysfunction, and to a large extent H63D Syndrome symptoms offers no room for skepticism regarding its existence. The strikingly obvious and clear clinical manifestations, pathophysiological markers, and intricate metabolic pathways elucidate a comprehensive disease model that intersects immunological, neurological, and metabolic domains. Moreover, the well-documented use of off-label, non-hepatotoxic pharmaceuticals to modulate and manage the symptoms further substantiates the validity of the syndrome's medical characterization. However, the complexity of the disease calls for intensive, multi-disciplinary scientific research to unravel the specific mechanisms, possible correlations, and optimal therapeutic

interventions. Although we have made significant strides in understanding the disease at a meta-level, the details remain labyrinthine and require specialized focus for a more nuanced comprehension. It is essential to note that the trajectory for advancing our understanding of the syndrome and the treatment paradigms will largely depend on the endeavors of independent researchers and clinicians. Given that the syndrome is largely managed with off-patent pharmaceuticals, there is limited foreseeable interest from the pharmaceutical industry in investing in research or drug development for this particular condition. Consequently, it falls upon academic and clinical circles to continue driving the research agenda, both to deepen our understanding and to explore novel therapeutic avenues that can improve patient outcomes and quality of life.

Conflicts of interest

None declared.

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